

D8.11

Videos 1 project intro video + 1
new video per year to update
process + final conf video 2

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1. Overview of BBTWINS' videos

Deliverable D8.11 "Videos 1 project intro video + 1 new video per year to update process + final conf video 2" by REVOLVE MEDIA is a public demonstrator. It includes the following five videos:

1. The 'Project Intro Video' delivered in November 2021 (M6) – publicly available [via this link](#).
2. 'Project update video #1' delivered in November 2022 (M18) – publicly available [via this link](#)
3. 'Project update video #2' delivered in November 2023 (M30) – publicly available [via this link](#)
4. 'Project update video #3' delivered in November 2024 (M42) – publicly available [via this link](#)
5. 'Final conference video' to be delivered in May 2025 (M48) as part of the final conference. – the two sessions are publicly available. Session 1 is available [via this link](#) and session 2 can be accessed [via this link](#).

34 videos were planned based on the grant agreement (see Table 1 for a breakdown into different categories), the partner interviews category included in-person interviews with partners (15), shorter videos (3) where key aspects of the project were mentioned and animated videos (5) where the different technologies were explained more in-depth.

Table 1 Video KPIs as stated in the Grant Agreement

BBTWINS videos	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Total
Videos					34
Introductory project video	1				1
Yearly update video		1	1	1	3
Partner interviews	7	7	7	7	28
Use case highlight videos			1	1	2

These videos are published on BBTWINS's YouTube Playlist: [BBTWINS | Agri-Food Digitalisation](#) (see Figure 2), while some shorts were uploaded directly to the LinkedIn channel of the project. From YouTube, the videos have also been shared via the project's [LinkedIn](#), published on the [project website](#) and included in the BioByte [newsletters](#) in order to maximise impact.

Uploading videos directly to LinkedIn was a strategic choice aimed at maximizing professional engagement. Native videos are prioritized by LinkedIn’s algorithm, increasing visibility and reach. Autoplay functionality captures attention more effectively than external links. Additionally, LinkedIn provides detailed audience analytics, such as viewer job titles and locations, offering valuable insights for future videos and content to be created. The platform’s professional context ensures content is seen by a relevant and targeted audience. These factors collectively justified the use of native video uploads of short videos for greater impact and effectiveness.

Being public deliverables, videos are in .mp4 format or similar. The size of a good quality 2-minute video in .mp4 is around 125 MB. Even if compressed to .zip or similar formats, videos are normally larger than the maximum size of 52 MB for a single file allowed by the SyGMA online tool for reporting deliverables. Consequently, in addition to publishing videos via the REVOLVE YouTube Channel, BBTWINS’ videos have been formally reported in the form of a written report like the present one including a link to the corresponding, publicly available video. A list of all videos published and their reach reported at the time of report submission can be found in Annex A- List of videos on YouTube and their reach (28/04/2025).

Figure 1 BBTWINS YouTube playlist

2. Project Intro video

The project intro video has been designed as a general introduction to the project and the work that will be taking place over the next four years. The footage used introduces topics specific to the project – peach orchards and pig farms – while also showing more generic footage that places the project at the heart of the agri-food industry. This also presents the project’s work and future results as being applicable to the wider agri-food industry.

The video incorporates both free and paid footage, being efficient with our use of resources while also ensuring a high-quality video. We have also used footage taken by project partners, highlighting the work being done by the project and preventing the video from appearing too commercial.

REVOLVE has also developed a series of animations to highlight the digital aspects of the project and present the information in an accessible and digestible format.

Figure 2 - BBTWINS animation

The accessibility of the video is also reflected in its overall length – under two and a half minutes – highlighting the most important information but also holding the viewers’ attention.

Figure 3 - Peaches in a crate

The video also has an upbeat electronic soundtrack, representing the rhythm and purpose of the project while also keeping viewers engaged.

The video also includes all BBI JU and European Commission funding information, partner information and links to the project website and social media channels.

[The video can be viewed via the BBTWINS YouTube Playlist here.](#)

3. Update process videos

Three videos were published in Months 18, 30, and 42, respectively, to provide updates on the progress achieved by the project partners. Each video was carefully aligned with the timeline of the relevant work packages and was designed to highlight key preliminary results while safeguarding any confidential information that could potentially impact the rights and interests of the consortium.

In the third project year, particular emphasis was placed on enhancing the video's engagement level, with the aim of positioning it as a promotional piece for the final year of the project. This video primarily features a voiceover narrative supported by visual content gathered between June 2023 and May 2024. As in previous years, the video showcases key milestones from the reporting period and is supplemented with animation for greater visual impact. The video was planned to have a maximum duration of three minutes.

A detailed overview of the scriptwriting process of 'Project update video #3' is provided in Annex A. Links to all published videos are available below:

- 'Project update video #1' delivered in November 2022 (M18) – publicly available [via this link](#)
- 'Project update video #2' delivered in November 2023 (M30) – publicly available [via this link](#)
- 'Project update video #3' delivered in November 2024 (M42) – publicly available [via this link](#)

Figure 4 Progress update video thumbnails

4. Final conference video

The final BBTWINS conference showcased how digital innovations are reshaping the agri-food sector by enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and circularity of value chains. From AI and blockchain to interoperability and smart logistics, the event highlighted real-world applications of these technologies and their role in optimising processes across the entire value chain. A key focus of the discussions was the importance of involving producers early in the process to ensure digital solutions are both practical and effective in real-world scenarios.

Notable takeaways included the potential of waste valorisation, the advantages of real-time data for more informed decision-making, and the crucial need for interoperability and trust to support large-scale adoption. Full recordings and presentation slides from the event were made available [online](#) for those interested in revisiting the insights shared.

Considering the length of the event, the recording of the final conference was divided into two parts and each into specific chapters to ensure easy access to relevant sections.

- 'Final conference video - Session #1' was delivered in April 2025 – publicly available [via this link](#)
- 'Final conference video - Session #2' was delivered in April 2025 – publicly available [via this link](#)

Figure 5 Final conference video thumbnails

5. Annex

Annex A- List of videos on YouTube and their reach (28/04/2025)

# of video	Video Name	# of views
1	Digital Twins & Resource Recovery in Agri-Food BBTWINS (BBTWINS concept video)	202
2	Digital Twins & Resource Recovery in Agri-Food BBTWINS (Introductory video)	230
3	Ψηφιακά δίδυμα και ανάκτηση πόρων (GR) BBTWINS (concept video in Greek)	53
4	Ψηφιοποίηση της Αλυσίδας Αξίας Αγοδιατροφής για Αποδοτικότητα Πόρων (GR) BBTWINS (Introductory video in Greek)	42
5	How Digital Twins Are Reshaping Food Industries BBTWINS	721
6	Increasing Traceability in Food Production With Digital Twins BBTWINS	249
7	Preparing Digitalisation of Agri-Food Case Studies Year #1 BBTWINS	138
8	Digitalisation for More Efficient Agri-Food Supply Chains BBTWINS	193
9	Digital Twins Bridge Bioeconomy and Agri-Food Sectors BBTWINS	165
10	Valorising Agri-Food Waste Through Digitalisation BBTWINS	101
11	How Digital Twins Benefit People, Planet, and Business BBTWINS	98
12	Preparing Agri-Food Industries for the Future BBTWINS	123
13	New Mentalities for the Agri-Food Industry BBTWINS	132
14	Digitalisation Creating New Opportunities in Agriculture BBTWINS	104
15	Cutting-Edge Agri-Food Technologies in Practice Year #2 BBTWINS	177
16	Creating Resource-Efficient Value Chains Interview with Dr. Luis Pinto Ferreira 	100
17	Benefits of Waste Valorisation for the Agri-Food Sector BBTWINS	109
18	Innovative Waste Valorisation in Agri-Food BBTWINS	287
19	Rethinking Agri-food Logistics BBTWINS	107
20	Webinar: Digital Twin Transitions in Agri-Food BBTWINS	412
22	Case Study: Digitalising Pork Value Chain BBTWINS	195
23	Future of Farming is on the Way 5 Highlights of Year #3 BBTWINS	129
24	Digital Twin Prototype	45
25	How Are Clusters Connecting Farmers to Make an Impact? Yannis Fallas BBTWINS	50
26	Case Study: Digitalised Peach Value Chain BBTWINS	113
27	Blockchain Traceability for the Agri-Food Sector BBTWINS	94
28	Digital Technologies for a Resilient Agri-Food Sector (Session 1) BBTWINS	77
29	Digital Technologies for a Resilient Agri-Food Sector (Session 2) BBTWINS	66
	Total views	4512